

A Bibliometric Analysis of Studies on Silver Tourism Literature

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Keywords: Silver Tourism, Senior Tourism, Third Age Tourism, Bibliometric Analysis, Web of Science, VOSviewer

JEL Codes: L83, Z32, D83
Research Article

Yavuz, Akçay, H. (2026). A Bibliometric Analysis of Studies on Silver Tourism Literature, Health Tourism Journal, 2(1), 37-59.

Abstract

Global demographic changes and increasing life expectancy are gradually increasing the importance of the silver tourism market in the tourism sector. The purpose of this study is to reveal the conceptual evolution and current research trends of the silver tourism literature through bibliometric analysis. A total of 216 academic publications retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection database were analysed using VOSviewer software. A thesaurus was employed during the analysis process to improve data reliability and terminological consistency. The study employs co-occurrence and co-citation analyses to map the intellectual and thematic structure of the field. The findings indicate that silver tourism research gained significant momentum especially since 2016, concentrated in the 2021-2025 period, and countries such as China, the USA, Spain, Australia and Portugal are among the leading contributors to the literature. The keyword network shows that the literature is shaped around themes such as senior tourism, well-being, active ageing, motivation, travel constraints, and social tourism. This study provides a strategic roadmap for academia and tourism industry stakeholders regarding the future research directions of the silver tourism market.

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Received Date: 05.08.2026

Accepted Date: 06.24.2026

1.Introduction

In recent decades, the global demographic structure has undergone a significant transformation, with a steady increase in the proportion of the ageing population, thereby enhancing the importance of older adults within the tourism economy (Büyük et al., 2022). According to the latest World Population Prospects 2024 report published by the United Nations (UN), older age cohorts represent the fastest-growing demographic group worldwide due to rising life expectancy. Projections suggest that by the 2030s, the number of individuals aged 80 and over is expected to surpass the population of infants under one year of age, while by the 2080s, the population aged 65 and above is projected to exceed that of individuals under 18 (UN, 2024).

This demographic shift has led to the emergence of the “silver economy” within broader economic systems, while simultaneously positioning older adults as a strategic and sustainable market segment within the tourism industry. In this context, ageing is no longer viewed solely as a burden on social security systems; rather, it is increasingly recognized as a driver of sustainable development and a source of new market opportunities (Bal et al., 2025).

Silver tourism extends beyond an individual consumption preference and constitutes a global phenomenon supported by national policies and international initiatives. For instance, programs such as Spain’s IMSERSO initiative, which promotes off-season travel among older adults (Sedgley et al., 2018), and China’s Starlight Program, aimed at improving the well-being of older individuals (Chen, 2009), illustrate the institutionalization of this market. At the global level, the World Health Organization’s declaration of 2021-2030 as the “Decade of Healthy Ageing,” along with initiatives such as the Age-Friendly Cities and Communities Network, further highlights the strategic importance of this segment (Coşkun, 2019; Özmete, 2022; WHO, 2026).

Despite its growing demographic, economic, and social relevance, bibliometric studies that systematically examine the evolution of academic interest in silver tourism, identify its dominant thematic orientations, and map its intellectual structure remain relatively limited. In particular, a comprehensive understanding of how the field has developed over time, which actors and institutions have shaped its trajectory, and how research themes have evolved is still emerging.

In this regard, identifying the disciplinary intersections within the literature and the key works shaping its theoretical foundations is essential for assessing the maturity and development of the field. Accordingly, the primary aim of this study is to examine the silver tourism literature through a bibliometric approach in order to reveal its scientific development dynamics. Specifically, the study aims to (i) identify publication trends, (ii) analyse prominent authors, institutions, and countries, (iii) uncover the thematic structure through keyword co-occurrence and citation network analyses, and (iv) map structural gaps in silver tourism research to provide a strategic perspective for both academia and the tourism industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conceptual Framework of Silver Tourism

Ageing is defined as the totality of irreversible structural and functional changes that occur in the organism over time, whereas old age represents a multidimensional process characterized by a decline in biological capacities (Bulut et al., 2012; Yerli, 2017). The concept and boundaries of old age may vary across disciplines and international organizations. While the United Nations (UN) considers individuals aged 60 and over as older adults, the World Health Organization (WHO) defines the onset of old age as 65 years. With increasing life expectancy, older populations are often categorized into subgroups, including the young-old (65-74), the old (75-84), and the oldest-old (85 and above) (Oğuz et al., 2019). In the literature, silver tourism is conceptualized as a multidimensional construct that refers to the participation of older age groups in tourism activities. It generally encompasses individuals aged 55 and over who engage in travel driven by motivations such as maintaining health, enhancing quality of life, and utilizing leisure time within the framework of active ageing (Türkoğlu, 2026). In addition, this form of tourism includes activities undertaken by individuals who require care due to advanced age or disability, particularly to access health and well-being services such as rehabilitation, medical treatment, and occupational therapy (Republic of Türkiye Ministry of Health, 2011; Ataman et al., 2017). In the national literature, this field is described using various terms, including senior tourism, third-age tourism, and geriatric tourism (Bektaş et al., 2016), as well as elderly tourism and elderly care tourism. In the international literature, this terminological diversity expands further, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of the field through concepts such as Third-Age Tourism, Mature Tourism, Silver Tourism, Age-Friendly Tourism, Active Ageing Tourism, Elderly Tourism, Grey Tourism, and Senior Tourism (Aydemir et al., 2018). Particularly within the European Union context, the concepts of “silver tourism” and the “silver economy” have gained increasing prominence. This diversity indicates that the field extends beyond a simple age-based segmentation and instead represents a broader consumption domain shaped by individuals’ life stages, health conditions, care needs, and socio-economic characteristics. The concept of silver tourism is closely associated with the active ageing perspective, which constitutes an important theoretical framework for understanding this phenomenon. The active ageing model, introduced by the WHO (2002), emphasizes sustaining older adults’ participation in society while maintaining autonomy and independence in later life (Paul et al., 2012). Within this framework, participation in tourism activities, not only for leisure but also for rehabilitation, well-being, and therapeutic purposes, can be considered an important contributor to the active ageing process

(Kara, 2020)

2.2. Behavioural Dynamics of Senior Tourists

The travel behaviour of older tourists differs from that of other age groups. This segment, which constitutes a significant consumer group in contemporary tourism, is internally heterogeneous, varying in terms of age ranges, behavioural patterns, and expectations. Accordingly, the tourism literature employs a range of classifications to describe this cohort, including “new senior citizens,” “young-old,” “woopies” (well-off older individuals), “baby boomers,” the “in-between generation,” and the “grey market” (Çataloğlu, 2020). This terminological diversity suggests that senior tourism is multidimensional and that older tourists cannot be treated as a homogeneous group with uniform expectations. This emerging tourist profile tends to spend accumulated retirement income and increased leisure time more freely, thereby playing an important role in global leisure mobility (Cankül, 2015). In the literature, the ability of older tourists to travel during off-season periods and their tendency toward experience-oriented consumption are frequently highlighted as key advantages. Conversely, age-related mobility limitations, safety concerns, comfort expectations, and chronic health conditions are identified as major travel constraints (Baş, 2016). Furthermore, motivation-based studies indicate that the travel behaviour of older tourists is largely associated with needs such as health maintenance, relaxation, social interaction, and self-actualization.

2.3. General Evaluation of the Literature

An overall evaluation of the literature reveals that the field of silver tourism has evolved across conceptual, behavioural, health-related, and economic dimensions. This thematic diversity highlights the multidimensional nature of the field and illustrates that it has been shaped by contributions from various disciplines. Nevertheless, considering the dynamic structure of the silver tourism market and the recent growth of the literature in parallel with global demographic shifts, it is necessary to reassess the current state, thematic evolution, and level of intellectual development of the field through a more comprehensive dataset. Furthermore, an examination of the geographical distribution of the literature indicates that research is largely concentrated along the Asia-Pacific axis and in developed Western countries, revealing a notable imbalance in global representation.

2.5. Aim and Scope of the Research

The primary aim of this study is to identify, from a holistic perspective and through bibliometric methods, the developmental trends in the silver tourism literature and the level of intellectual maturity the field has reached. Compared with previous research, this study aims to delineate the boundaries of the field by employing an expanded terminology pool consisting of 20 different keywords and to generate transparent and robust thematic network maps by refining the dataset with a thesaurus. In this respect, by mapping the

current state of the silver tourism literature, its author and institutional collaboration patterns, and its conceptual trajectory, which have developed under various concepts, using the most up-to-date data, this research provides readers with a comprehensive state-of-the-field overview.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Method

In this study, the bibliometric analysis method was employed to examine the structural and thematic characteristics of the silver tourism literature. Bibliometric analysis is an analytical approach that enables global research trends to be understood by quantitatively analysing large volumes of scientific data through mathematical and statistical techniques (Alsharif et al., 2020; Kazak et al., 2023). In recent years, the increasing availability of comprehensive databases such as Web of Science (WoS), together with the widespread use of software tools such as VOSviewer, has rapidly increased the popularity of this method in the social sciences (Donthu et al., 2021). Mapping the growing body of scientific literature through this method provides a strategic foundation for the present research by enabling the identification of collaborations among researchers and institutions, the analysis of thematic relationships, and the reliable mapping of the current state of established research domains (Ellegaard, 2018).

3.2. Data Collection Process and Search Strategy

The Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database was used as the data source for this study. The WoS database is widely preferred in academic research due to its coverage of high-impact journals, the reliability of its citation data, and the suitability of its data structure for bibliometric analyses (Mongeon et al., 2016). To capture the literature encompassing silver tourism as broadly as possible, a comprehensive search was conducted in the “Topic” field of the WoS database using the following keywords:

"silver tourism" OR "senior tourism" OR "elderly tourism" OR "grey tourism" OR "gray tourism" OR "gerontotourism" OR "geronto-tourism" OR "third age tourism" OR "golden age tourism" OR "geriatric tourism" OR "active aging tourism" OR "active ageing tourism" OR "age friendly tourism" OR "retirement tourism" OR "pensioner tourism" OR "baby boomer tourism" OR "boomer tourism" OR "late-life tourism" OR "older adult tourism" OR "senior friendly tourism"

To ensure the scientific quality and reliability of the retrieved data, the analysis was limited to English-language academic publications indexed in the Web of Science database. The final dataset included articles, review articles, early access publications, book chapters, and proceeding papers.

The data were retrieved on April 22, 2026. In order to avoid potential deviations arising from dynamic

database updates, the data extraction process was conducted within a single time period to ensure data consistency. As a result of the search and filtering process, a total of 216 academic publications that fully met the research protocol were identified and included in the final analysis. To enhance the transparency and reproducibility of the bibliometric search and screening process, a PRISMA-style flow diagram is presented in Figure 3.1. The diagram summarizes the main stages of data identification, screening, duplicate record control, thesaurus-based data standardization, and final inclusion, culminating in the final dataset of 216 publications.

Figure 3.1. PRISMA-Style Flow Diagram of the Bibliometric Search and Screening Process

3.3. Data Analysis and Visualization (Bibliometric Mapping)

The complete bibliographic records of the 216 retrieved publications, including author information, titles, abstracts, cited references, and keywords, were exported from the WoS database in plain text format. VOSviewer software, which is widely used in bibliometric research, was employed for the analysis and clustering of the data, as well as for the generation of bibliometric network maps. This software is recognized as a standard tool in bibliometric studies because of its ability to process complex citation, collaboration, and co-occurrence networks in scientific literature through text-mining techniques and transform them into distance-based visual maps (Eck et al., 2010).

Prior to the analysis, the retrieved dataset underwent specific data-cleaning procedures to enhance reliability. First, duplicate records resulting from different indexing processes were removed from the dataset. Subsequently, to improve the structural accuracy of the bibliometric maps and prevent terminology clutter, a custom thesaurus file was integrated into VOSviewer. This procedure enabled the consolidation of singular–plural variations, such as “senior tourist” and “senior tourists”, as well as spelling differences between American and British English, such as “aging” and “ageing”, under unified terms, thereby reducing potential algorithmic deviations. This process contributes to obtaining more meaningful and consistent results, particularly in keyword analyses (Donthu et al., 2021). The minimum threshold for keyword occurrences in the analyses was set to 5.

Within the scope of the study, the data were analysed in terms of publication year, document type, WoS index, WoS category, research area, country/region, institution, and publication sources. To identify the thematic trends and current focal points of the field, keyword co-occurrence analysis was conducted. In addition, author co-citation and document co-citation analyses were performed to reveal the intellectual structure of the literature and its foundational schools of thought. In the resulting network maps, the size of the nodes represents the frequency or citation strength of the respective item (word, author, or document) while the thickness of the links between the nodes indicates the strength of the connection and the degree of co-occurrence or co-citation between the items. The colours distinguishing the clusters from one another were automatically assigned by the software’s clustering algorithm based on their degree of statistical proximity

3.4. Scope and Limitations of the Research

This study is limited to publications indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database. WoS was preferred because it provides structured citation data, includes journals with recognized academic standards, and is widely used in bibliometric research. However, relying on a single database also has some limitations. Studies indexed only in other databases such as Scopus, PubMed, Google Scholar, or national databases may not have been included in the analysis. This may especially affect the visibility of regional

journals, non-English publications, book-based studies, and research from countries where tourism-related publications are not extensively covered by WoS. Therefore, the geographical and institutional patterns identified in this study should be interpreted as reflecting the silver tourism literature represented in the WoS Core Collection, rather than the entire global literature on the subject.

Another limitation concerns the keyword-based search strategy. Although a broad set of keywords was used to capture the field as comprehensively as possible, some studies using different terminology may have remained outside the dataset. In addition, bibliometric analysis is useful for identifying publication trends, thematic patterns, and intellectual structures, but it does not provide a detailed qualitative evaluation of the content of each individual study. Future research may address these limitations by comparing data from different databases, including Scopus and national databases, and by combining bibliometric mapping with systematic review or qualitative content analysis.

4.FINDINGS

This section analyses the bibliometric data of the 216 academic publications retrieved in accordance with the research protocol. The analysis is structured according to publication year, document type, index, research area, most productive countries and institutions, and publication sources.

4.1. Distribution of Publications by Year and Document Type

An examination of the temporal development of the silver tourism literature shows that the first studies appeared in the early 1990s (1992, 1994), while interest in the field has increased over time. Following the early period, when the number of studies was relatively limited, a clear upward trend in publication volume can be observed, particularly after 2010; however, the main scientific momentum appears to have begun in 2016 (see Chart 4.1). This increase can be considered closely related to the growing visibility of global ageing and the increasing interest in new market segments within tourism research.

Chart 4.1. Distribution of Publication Counts by Year

An examination of Chart 4.1 reveals that the number of publications in the literature entered a pronounced upward trend, particularly from 2019 onwards, reaching its peak in 2023 with 24 publications. Specifically, 23 publications were recorded in both 2021 and 2025, while 22 publications were published in 2024. Furthermore, the inclusion of five publications from 2026 in the dataset underscores the contemporary relevance of the field and the continuing strong interest of researchers in the topic (see Chart 4.1). This steady increase in publication volume in recent years can be interpreted as an indication that the silver tourism research domain is beginning to show a tendency toward intellectual maturity. Nevertheless, periodic fluctuations between years should also be considered in relation to global developments and macro-level shifts in research agendas.

Table 4.1. Document Types

Nr.	Document Types	Nr. of Publ.
1	Article	203
2	Early Access	15
3	Review Article	13
4	Book Chapters	12
5	Proceeding Paper	1

Note: Since some studies in the Web of Science database are indexed under more than one document type (e.g., Article and Early Access), the total value in the table exceeds the net number of publications analysed (216).

An examination of the document types within the dataset of 216 studies shows that the vast majority consisted of research articles (203 publications), followed by early access publications (15 publications) and review articles (13 publications).

4.2. Indices, Categories and Research Areas

An analysis of the index distribution of the publications reveals that the literature has developed in outlets with high scientific impact. More than half of the examined studies, corresponding to 120 publications, are indexed in the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), which is considered one of the most prestigious indexes. This is followed by the Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) with 75 publications and the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED) with 21 publications (see Chart 4.2).

Chart 4.2. WoS Index Distribution

An examination of the WoS categories shows that “Hospitality, Leisure, Sport, and Tourism” ranks first with 143 publications. This category is followed by “Management” with 28 publications, “Business” with 24 publications, and “Environmental Studies” with 18 publications. In terms of broader research areas, “Social Sciences – Other Topics” with 149 publications and “Business & Economics” with 56 publications stand out as the most prominent fields (see Table 4.2).

Table 4.2. WoS Categories

Nr.	Web of Science Categories	Nr. of Public.
1	Hospitality Leisure Sport Tourism	143
2	Management	28
3	Business	24
4	Environmental Studies	18
5	Environmental Sciences	13
6	Green Sustainable Science Technology	12
7	Sociology	10
8	Economics	8
9	Geography	6
10	Social Sciences Interdisciplinary	6
11	Gerontology	5
12	Public Environmental Occupational Health	4
13	Transportation	3
14	Computer Science Artificial Intelligence	2
15	Humanities Multidisciplinary	2

4.3. Most Prolific Authors and the Most Influential Studies in the Literature

To assess individual-level productivity and scientific impact within the silver tourism literature, the most prolific authors in the dataset were analysed. An examination of Table 4.3 reveals that Ian Patterson, with 8 publications, made the greatest quantitative contribution to the development of the field. Patterson is followed by Adela Balderas with 7 publications, and by Elisa Alen, Osvaldo Silva, and Jinsoo Hwang with 5 publications each. Further down the list, Maria Helena de Aguiar Pereira e Pestana, Dominik Huber, Ping Hou, Teresa Medeiros, and Nieves Losada, each with 4 publications, stand out as prominent contributors to the literature.

Table 4.3. Most Prolific Authors

Nr.	Most Prolific Authors	Nr. of Public.
1	Patterson, Ian	8
2	Balderas, Adela	7
3	Alen, Elisa	5
4	Silva, Osvaldo	5
5	Hwang, Jinsoo	5
6	de Aguiar Pereira e Pestana, Maria Helena	4
7	Huber, Dominik	4
8	Hou, Ping	4
9	Medeiros, Teresa	4
10	Losada, Nieves	4

To identify the core reference sources shaping the intellectual structure of the silver tourism literature and the studies with the highest scientific impact, a document citation analysis was conducted (see Table 4.4). According to the quantitative findings obtained from the Web of Science database, the publication with the highest citation frequency in the literature is Kim, Woo, and Uysal's (2015) study titled "Tourism experience and quality of life among elderly tourists", with 328 citations. This pioneering study is followed by the motivation-oriented conceptual model developed by Jang et al. (2009), with 249 citations, and the market segmentation study conducted by Hsu et al. (2007), with 227 citations.

Table 4.4. Most Cited Authors and Publications with the Highest Citation Frequencies

Nr.	Most Cited Authors	Publications with the Highest Citation Frequencies	Nr. Of Public.
1	Kim, H.; Woo, E.; Uysal, M.	Tourism experience and quality of life among elderly tourists	328
2	Jang, S.; Bai, B.; Hu, C.; Wu, C.	Affect, travel motivation, and travel intention: A senior market	249
3	Hsu, C.; Cai, L.; Wong, K.	A model of senior tourism motivations - Anecdotes from Beijing and Shanghai	227
4	Hwang, J.; Lee, J.	A strategy for enhancing senior tourists' well-being perception	187
5	Pestana, M.; Parreira, A.; Moutinho, L.	Motivations, emotions and satisfaction: The keys to a tourism destination choice	172

**4.4.
Most**

Productive Countries and Institutions

An examination of the author-, institution-, and country-level distributions shows that the senior tourism literature is concentrated around specific academic centres at the global level. Country-level analyses indicate that the studies are largely clustered in developed countries and regions with well-established tourism industries.

Chart 4.3. Most Productive Countries

In this context, an analysis of the countries contributing the highest number of publications to the field shows that China (PEOPLES R CHINA) stands out prominently with 63 publications. China is followed by the USA with 32 publications, Spain with 26 publications, Australia with 23 publications, and Portugal with 21 publications (see Chart 4.3). The prominence of European countries such as Spain and Portugal, as well as Asia-Pacific countries such as China and Australia, can be directly associated with both their ageing demographic structures and their advanced tourism infrastructures.

Table 4.5. Most Productive Institutions

Nr.	Most Productive Institutions	Nr. of Public.
1	HONG KONG POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY	11
2	UNIVERSITY OF QUEENSLAND	10
3	SEJONG UNIVERSITY	7
4	MACAO UNIVERSITY OF TOURISM	6
5	UNIVERSIDADE DE VIGO	6
6	UNIVERSIDADE DOS ACORES	6
7	VIRGINIA POLYTECHNIC INSTITUTE STATE UNIVERSITY	6
8	AUCKLAND UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY	5
9	HANGZHOU CITY UNIVERSITY	5
10	INSTITUTO UNIVERSITARIO DE LISBOA	5

At the institutional level, universities and research centres stand out as the main actors shaping the literature (see Table 4.5). An analysis of institutional productivity shows that Hong Kong Polytechnic University in China was the leading contributing institution, with 11 publications. It was followed by the University of Queensland in Australia with 10 publications, Sejong University in South Korea with 7 publications, Macao University of Tourism in China with 6 publications, and Universidade de Vigo in Portugal with 6 publications. This distribution indicates that the most productive researchers represent key research groups guiding the development of the field and that international scientific collaborations are largely shaped around these leading institutions.

4.5. Leading Publication Sources

An examination of the journals with the highest number of publications in the silver tourism literature shows that *Current Issues in Tourism* ranks first with 16 publications. It is followed by *Sustainability and Tourism Review*, each with 9 publications. *Anatolia* with 8 publications, *Tourism Management* with 7 publications, *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research* with 6 publications, *Journal of Vacation Marketing* with 6 publications, and *Tourism Management Perspectives* with 6 publications were identified as other key journals contributing to the development of the field (see Table 4.6).

Table 4.6. Leading Publication Sources

Nr.	Leading Publication Sources	Nr. of Publ.
1	CURRENT ISSUES IN TOURISM	16
2	SUSTAINABILITY	9
3	TOURISM REVIEW	9
4	ANATOLIA INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY RESEARCH	8
5	TOURISM MANAGEMENT	7
6	ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF TOURISM RESEARCH	6
7	JOURNAL OF VACATION MARKETING	6
8	TOURISM MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVES	6
9	TOURISM RECREATION RESEARCH	6
10	ANNALS OF TOURISM RESEARCH	5

4.6. Bibliometric Network Analyses

This section presents the findings of the keyword co-occurrence, author co-citation, and document co-citation analyses conducted to reveal the thematic structure and intellectual development dynamics of the silver tourism literature. The analyses were performed using VOSviewer software, and the resulting network maps were interpreted on the basis of nodes, links, and clusters.

4.6.1. Keyword Co-occurrence Analysis

Keyword co-occurrence analysis aims to identify the thematic structure of the field by revealing the relationships among concepts that are used together in the literature. In this context, the literature was found to be structured around four main thematic clusters (see Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.1. Keyword Co-occurrence Network

An examination of Figure 4.1 shows that the concept of “senior tourism”, which has the largest node, occupies a central position in the literature. This core concept, when considered together with “travel constraints”, points to the structural boundaries of the market. The nodes “seniors”, “motivation”, “tourism”, “ageing”, and “social tourism” in the red cluster indicate that the studies mainly focus on the travel motivations of older individuals and the social dimension of tourism. The green cluster links the concepts of “well-being” and “active ageing” with “tourism development”, reflecting the positive outcomes of silver tourism in relation to health and quality of life. The blue cluster, represented by the nodes “China” and “leisure travel”, indicates that China-oriented leisure travel studies constitute a distinct sub-theme within the literature. When the network is evaluated as a whole, the strong links among “senior tourism”, “well-being”, and “motivation” suggest that these concepts form one of the main theoretical axes of senior tourism research.

4.6.2. Author Co-citation Analysis

Author co-citation analysis aims to reveal the intellectual structure and theoretical background of the field by identifying researchers who are frequently cited together in the literature. In the map, authors who are often co-cited are grouped into clusters of the same colour (see Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2. Author Co-citation Network

An examination of Figure 4.2 shows that the Patterson node is located at the centre of the network and has the highest citation frequency. This indicates that the author intersects with all other clusters in the field of silver tourism and has become one of the main reference points of the field. The map further shows that the field has developed around four main clusters that are highly interactive with one another:

- Red cluster: This cluster represents one of the highly cited schools of thought in the literature and includes authors such as Fleischer, Shoemaker, Jang, Hsu, and Moschis. The studies of these researchers form a dense intellectual collaboration network through frequent mutual citations.
- Yellow cluster: Located in the upper part of the network, this cluster includes prominent authors such as Nimrod, Morgan, McCabe, and Jackson.
- Green cluster: This dense cluster, consisting of authors such as Kim, Huber, Hwang, Wen, and Otoo, represents one of the largest and most internally interactive structures in the field. The high link density and node clustering suggest that these authors are concentrated around specific research themes.
- Blue cluster: The blue cluster serves as a bridge between the green and yellow clusters. By including institutional actors such as the European Commission and specific researchers, it connects different theoretical approaches within the literature.

At this point, it is important to emphasize the methodological distinction between absolute citation counts (see Table 4.4) and node sizes in the co-citation network (see Figure 4.2). While researchers such as Kim, Uysal, and Jang rank at the top of the list of most-cited individual studies, Patterson's emergence as the

largest node at the centre of the co-citation network is a structural result of the algorithm. Co-citation analysis does not measure the total number of citations received by individual articles; rather, it measures the frequency with which authors are cited together in reference lists. Owing to his quantitative productivity in the field (8 publications), Patterson appears as a common reference point in the bibliographies of almost all sub-clusters in the literature, including health, motivation, and policy, thereby occupying a central author position that connects different schools of thought within the field.

Overall, the author co-citation network indicates that the silver tourism literature has developed not as a single homogeneous structure, but around four distinct, polycentric, and mutually reinforcing theoretical clusters with strong internal citation links.

4.6.3. Document Co-citation Analysis

In addition to authors, document co-citation analysis was conducted to identify the studies that form the theoretical foundation of silver tourism (see Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3. Document Co-citation Network

An examination of Figure 4.3 shows that the literature is divided into two main periods, represented by the

red and green clusters, which appear to be mutually reinforcing in chronological and thematic terms. When the years indicated in the node labels are examined, the works in this cluster are seen to have been published predominantly between 1989 and 2009. At the centre of this cluster, the studies by Fleischer (2002; $f=51$) and Huang (2003; $f=40$) stand out as the works receiving the highest number of co-citations. The green cluster on the right side of the map, on the other hand, reflects more recent studies that constitute the modern theoretical background of silver tourism. An evaluation of the node sizes in the map shows that this cluster is concentrated around the works of authors such as Alen et al. (2017) and Huber (2018).

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this study, the silver tourism literature, which has become one of the most strategic markets in the tourism industry in line with demographic transformations, was examined through bibliometric analysis. Within the scope of the research, the conceptual background, author productivity, and citation networks of current international studies indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) database were evaluated. The findings indicate that the literature is geographically and institutionally clustered around specific centres. China stands out as the most productive country in the literature, followed by the USA, Spain, and Australia. At the institutional level, Hong Kong Polytechnic University emerges as the leading institution.

When author productivity and scientific impact analyses are considered, Ian Patterson appears as the most prolific author and occupies a central position in the author co-citation network. However, article-based citation analyses indicate that studies by Kim, Woo, and Uysal (2015), Jang et al. (2009), and Hsu et al. (2007) have the highest impact values in the literature. In addition, the presence of authors from different disciplines who are positioned outside the main clusters of the citation network suggests that silver tourism is not limited solely to tourism management, but has developed an interdisciplinary structure through strong interactions with sociology, gerontology, and health sciences. Existing international research is clustered in specific geographical areas. To achieve a more holistic understanding of the potential of silver tourism, increasing research in developing countries with rapidly ageing demographic structures and strong health tourism infrastructures would be beneficial.

The theoretical contribution of this study is that it makes the conceptual organization of silver tourism research more visible. By using an expanded keyword strategy and thesaurus-based standardization, the study brings together different terms used in the literature, including gerontotourism, active ageing tourism, third-age tourism, and senior tourism, within a common analytical frame. This helps to show that the field has developed through multiple but related conceptual labels rather than through a single dominant terminology. In addition, the bibliometric maps provide a structured overview of the main thematic orientations and intellectual connections shaping the field. In this respect, the study contributes to future research by indicating how silver tourism can be examined not only as a market segment, but also in relation

to ageing, well-being, accessibility, inclusion, and destination planning.

The main limitation of this study is that the analyses were limited to the Web of Science (WoS) database in order to provide a global overview. To identify the developmental trajectory of national literature, future studies could make a significant contribution to the field by incorporating national databases or alternative databases and search platforms, such as Scopus.

A thematic examination of the most cited studies indicates that the literature is concentrated in certain areas. The current studies mainly focus on psychosocial variables such as the travel motivations of older tourists, quality of life, well-being, and experience satisfaction. In contrast, the results of the topic-based analysis, namely Citation Topics Micro, show that 79.2% of the literature focuses on general tourism impacts, while some critical areas are represented at rates below 1% (see Table 5.1).

Table 5.1. Micro Citation Topics

Nr.	Micro Citation Topics	Nr. of Public.
1	Tourism Impacts	172
2	Consumer Behavior	7
3	Subjective Well-being	6
4	Ageism	2
5	Geriatric Nutrition	2
6	Grey Forecasting	2
7	Fuzzy Decision-making	2
8	Organizational Behavior	2
9	Dementia Caregivers	1
10	Ocular And Ballistic Trauma	1
11	Air Transport Systems	1
12	Urban Mobility	1
13	Retirement Economics	1
14	International Education	1
15	Poverty Gender Disparities	1
16	Lgbtq+ Intersectionality	1
17	Workplace Design	1
18	Religion's Impact	1
19	Foresight	1
20	Entrepreneurship	1
21	Industrial Conveyor Systems	1
22	Migration Dynamics	1
23	Urban Housing Dynamics	1
24	Regression Techniques	1

In light of these quantitative data, the following strategic recommendations are proposed for future research: Social inclusion and special needs: It is recommended that topics represented at very low rates in the literature, such as 0.4%, including ageism, poverty, and the travel experiences of individuals with dementia, be examined within the context of social justice. Rather than treating older adults as a homogeneous group, future studies focusing on these specific subgroups may contribute to deepening the literature.

Geriatric health and technical infrastructure: Greater attention should be given to topics that are relatively

underrepresented in the analyses, such as geriatric nutrition, urban mobility, and age-friendly transportation systems.

In particular, increasing interdisciplinary studies that address the physical accessibility of older tourists in destinations and their health-related needs from a technical perspective would make an important contribution to the literature.

Technological adaptation and foresight models: Digital transformation, including the use of VR/AR, and future-oriented strategic foresight models appear to be insufficiently represented in the context of silver tourism. Future research should therefore focus on emerging themes such as the technological adaptation of older tourists and artificial intelligence-supported predictive models.

Policy guidance and private-sector investment: The gradual ageing of the global population is turning silver tourism into a growing field of service provision and investment, with implications for both social policy and the tourism industry. Central and local governments should therefore incorporate age-friendly and accessible tourism into national and regional tourism strategies and establish guiding principles for universal design, accessible transport, health and emergency services, off-season social tourism programmes, and service standards tailored to older visitors. Age-friendly hotels, rehabilitation and care centres, accessible accommodation facilities, and thermal and wellness investments should be treated as priority areas within relevant incentive schemes. The private sector should also be encouraged to develop services that respond to the diverse needs of older travellers in areas such as accommodation, transport, rehabilitation, wellness, insurance, digital assistance, and personalised travel planning. Public-private partnerships may further support the development of accessible infrastructure, staff training in communication and care for older tourists, and cooperation with international insurance providers. From this perspective, silver tourism should be viewed not simply as a commercial opportunity, but as a responsible area of investment that can strengthen the independence, social participation, travel experiences, and quality of life of older adults.

This study reveals the multilayered character of the silver tourism literature by analysing it holistically through thematic and intellectual network structures, rather than limiting the analysis to descriptive indicators alone. The findings show that the literature is concentrated around specific thematic axes, whereas some interdisciplinary research areas are relatively underrepresented. In this context, future studies moving beyond the general impacts of tourism and focusing on more specific and interdisciplinary topics - such as the decision-making processes of older individuals, their health-related needs, risks of social exclusion, and urban accessibility- may contribute to enhancing both the theoretical depth and the practical application capacity of the field.

Declaration of Research and Publication Ethics

Hülya Yavuz Akçay declare that this study does not require ethics committee approval. The research was conducted in compliance with national and international research and publication ethics

Author Contribution Rate Statement

Hülya Yavuz Akçay declares that they are the sole contributor to this manuscript and assume full responsibility for its content

Declaration of Conflict of Interest

Hülya Yavuz Akçay declares no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

Funding Declaration

Hülya Yavuz Akçay received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

Data Availability Statement

The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Usage Declaration

Hülya Yavuz Akçay used translation solely for tools to draft, translate or significantly edit portions of the text. Hülya Yavuz Akçay assume full responsibility for the factual accuracy and originality of the final content.

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